

PHYSIOLOGICAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL RESPONSES OF 'TRAKYA ILKEREN' GRAPEVINES TO SEAWEED (*Ascophyllum nodosum* L.) EXTRACT PULVERIZATIONS UNDER CONTINENTAL CLIMATE CONDITION

 Zeki Turkoz¹

¹Selcuk University Agriculture Faculty Horticulture Department Konya, Türkiye

*Corresponding Author:

E-mail: asabir@selcuk.edu.tr

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ABSTRACT. Multiple environmental stressors pressurized the agriculturists to implement much more fertilizers, pesticides and waters for higher production. Such an intensified agriculture technique threatens the natural sources and exacerbates the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture. Therefore, this study was performed to investigate the effects of different concentrations (0.0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0%) of foliar seaweed extract, a natural plant biostimulator, pulverizations on grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L. cv. Trakya ilkeren) physiology and development under the multiple stressors of continental climate condition. A total of nine homogenously grown plants in three replication per treatment was used. As the seaweed substance, 100% water soluble extract of *Ascophyllum nodosum* L. (0.1% N, 4% K₂O, plant hormones, vitamins and enzymes) was used. Seaweed treatments were performed three times with one month interval, beginning from the early vegetative development stage. Among the doses, 0.3% and 0.5% providing similar results, were the most effective applications in improving the leaf stomatal conductance (gs), although higher seaweed doses were also beneficial for several parameters. The seaweed applied at 0.3% dose the greatest effects on the leaf chlorophyll concentration, leaf area, shoot length and shoot diameter. Therefore, application of the 0.3% seaweed on grapevine leaf would be recommended as eco-friendly sustainable practice for a precision viticulture under the effects of environmental adversities.

Keywords: *Viticulture, plant stressors, precision agriculture, plant biostimulants*

INTRODUCTION

Temperature extremes and seasonal or long-term water deficit in agricultural lands, emerging from the global climate change, have been adversely influencing the grapevine physiology and growth throughout the world [1]. More frequent occurrence of the extreme weather conditions with a significant increase of the summer temperature and water shortage are estimated by most models, particularly for Mediterranean Regions [2], where the great majority of world grape production is carried out. In Europe, for example, certain growing regions are approaching to exceed the thresholds of optimum temperature and rainfall for grape growing [3]. Most of the grape growing zones in the world have been exposed to seasonal or long-term drought in conjunction with high temperature and radiation. Approximately, 1.8 billion people will be influenced with water deficit in the first quarter of the twenty-first century and 65% of the people will live with insufficient water [4]. Restrictions in natural sources forced the agriculturists to intensify food production practices to match the market demands of the increasing world population. In these endeavors, excessive use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides become a great environmental problem depleting the agricultural lands and disturbing the ecosystem balance [5]. The intensive agriculture techniques based on an overuse

of inputs, such as irrigation water, fertilizers and pesticides) and other improper cultivation practices have resulted in further degradation of agriculture area.

The European Community underlines the significance of scientific studies to increase public awareness on climate change and sustainable implementations in production [6]. Policy makers and agriculturists should implement climate-adaptive production strategies to sustain food demands of increasing world population under the effects of multiple stress factors. Plant breeding, the use of stress resistant genotypes, water saving strategies and the use of plant growth activators are among the precision agricultural techniques for the sustainable agriculture on the face of global climate change [7].

Plant growth promoting substances or biofertilizers have been recommended to support plant growth under the multiple stress factors. The foliar seaweed extract pulverization has been proven to be an effective environment-friendly practice on inducing plant growth and crop quality [8,9]. The seaweed extract, one of the most frequently studied substances in various plant species, has been recommended to use as an organic farm input in sustainable agriculture since they are ecologically safe and benign. Previous studies demonstrated that foliar seaweed application promoted the physiology and development of grapevine through improving the stomatal conductance and leaf chlorophyll concentration [10,11], with its essential plant nutrients, amino acids, cytokinins, vitamins, auxins, and abscisic acid [12]. Studies further indicate that seaweed (*Ascophyllum nodosum* L.) extract application improved the chlorophyll concentration in plant leaves [13], and increased the vegetative development and yield in peppers [14]. Therefore, it was hypothesized that foliar seaweed extract would mitigate stress and improve physiological traits under continental conditions. In spite of these facts, relatively insufficient publications are available in literature regarding the benefits of seaweed extracts on grapevines under stressed conditions.

Therefore, this study was conducted to investigate the effects of different concentrations of foliar seaweed pulverizations on the physiology and development of 'Trakya ilkeren' ('Alphonse Lavallée' × 'Perlette'), an early season fine table grape cultivar with blue-black color grown in various regions of Türkiye, under the stressors of continental climate condition in Konya, Türkiye.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental layout

The experiment was performed at the research and implementation vineyard (38°01.814 N, 032°30.546E, 1158m above sea level) of Selcuk University, Türkiye, in 2024. Climatic characteristic in the vineyard is arid/ semi-arid with cold winters, hot and dry summers. Annual mean temperature is around 12 °C. The highest temperature was 40.6 °C, while the lowest one was -28.2 °C. Annual average precipitation is approximately 330 mm, with a relative humidity generally below 50%, probably due to the common south wind and prevailing north wind are dry [15]. Table grape cultivars 'Trakya ilkeren' was selected for the study due to their extensive cultivation in Türkiye. One year old own-rooted vines were grown in a solid soilless culture established using nine liters (solid volume) pots containing the equal mixture of peat and perlite. Solid medium soilless culture was used in the study to minimize the effects of environmental variables and to focus on the effect of seaweed applied at different doses. Drip irrigation system with single emitter of about 4L h⁻¹ for each vine was installed to install a mild water stress condition as a prime feature of continental climate. The vine pots were isolated from the ground using black polyethylene sheets to prevent possible moisture efflux from the ground and to restrict weed growth. Homogenously grown plants were divided into six equal group each of which comprised nine plants.

The experiment was laid out on a randomized complete parcel design. Prior to the bud break, the vines were spur pruned leaving two buds each and after bud break single shoot per vine was allowed to grow to ensure homogenous plant growth for a logical comparison of treatment effects. Similar cultivation practices were performed to the study vines. To establish a mild drought stress condition, drip irrigations were programmed according to the soil water matric potential (Ψ_m). Soil tensiometers (The Irrrometer Company, Riverside, CA), inserted into a depth of approximately 15 cm, were continuously read from the beginning of the study (May) to the end of vegetation period (September) to control water level of growth medium. To adjust the first irrigation amount and frequency, water holding capacity level of soilless culture substrate was initially quantified as previously described by Satisha et al. [16]. Fifty percent of the calculated water holding level of the cultivation medium was considered for start levels of irrigation treatment [17]. Soil tensiometers were employed for a long-term precision controlling of substrate water depletion [18].

For drip irrigations, a tap water with a $\text{pH} \approx 7.3$ was applied to vines because natural water sources in general are alkaline in study region. Midday Ψ_m levels of growth substrate were maintained around 32 ± 6 cb as previously described by Sabir and Sari [19] who studied the effects of water deficit and zinc pulverization on the grapevine physiology and growth. A relatively higher air temperature (21–28 °C) and lower relative humidity (25–44%) (Ebro EBI 20 TH1) occurred in the study area during the experimental season as a typical semi-arid climate. An experiment in factorial design on six different seaweed doses, 0.0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0% with three replications (a total of nine plants per treatment) was conducted. As the seaweed extract, 100% water soluble extract of *Ascophyllum nodosum* L. containing mainly 0.1% N, 4% K_2O , plant hormones, vitamins and enzymes) was used. Treatments were performed three times with one month interval beginning at early vegetative development stage. The first seaweed pulverization for each experimental group was carried out when the shoots were about 20 cm long.

Investigations and Analyses

Physiology of the vines was measured three days after each treatment as well as two additional measurements after the last treatments. Stomatal conductance (g_s) and leaf temperature (T_{leaf}) were periodically during the summer season using the healthy sun exposed nine leaves per treatment born at the 5th–7th nodes on summer shoots [20] from the grapevines between 09:00 and 12:00h a.m. [21], with a mobile Model SC-1 leaf porometer (Decagon Pull man, WA, USA) [22] and was defined as $\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. At the same time, chlorophyll contents of the same mature leaves (at 5th–7th nodes) were recorded nondestructively using a portable chlorophyll meter (SPAD-502, Minolta, Japan). Nine fully expanded nondamaged mature leaves of each treatment were gathered when the shoot growth was approaching to cessation in the late summer for leaf area investigation. Using one set, leaf area was found with WinFolia computer image analysis system. Total shoot length and lignified shoot length were measured using a tape measure having a sensitivity of 1mm. Shoot diameter was determined with a digital caliper at a point 1cm above the second node. Diameter of the shoot was recorded with a digital caliper.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis using a randomized factorial design. Statistical tests were performed at $p < 0.05$ using SPSS 13.0 for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA), using the least significant difference (LSD) test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physiological Investigation

Seaweed extract pulverizations significantly improved the stomatal conductance (gs) of ‘Trakya ilkeren’ grapevines in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd measurement dates depending on the doses, although no significant changes were found for the 4th and 5th dates (Fig. 1). After the first application, the greatest gs was obtained from 0.3% doses ($151.1 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), while the lowest gs was observed in control vines ($101.6 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). For the second application, seaweed at 0.5% ($222.4 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) and 0.3% ($213.7 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) resulted in the greatest gs with similar positive effects. On the other hand, the gs value at 2.0% doses ($123.8 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) was ineffective with a close value to control ($131.4 \text{ mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Afterwards, the gs values presented a general decrease accompanied with the climate-dependent seasonal decrease in shoot development. During this period, 0.3% doses showed higher values than those of other doses in general, including control. The gs values recorded in the study are within the general ranges reported in previous studies performed on different grapevine cultivars [23]. Studies demonstrated that the gs greatly varies according to environmental climatic variables as well as genotypic and soil factors [21] and leaf seaweed pulverizations were also reported to improve the vine gs for both full irrigation and deficit irrigation conditions [24]. Among the doses, 0.3% and 0.5% were the most effective applications in improving the gs, while 2.0% doses did not affect the gs.

Fig. 1. Changes in stomatal conductance ($\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) of ‘Trakya ilkeren’ vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

Leaf temperature (T_{leaf}) of grapevines underwent a seasonal variations and seaweed doses slightly affected the T_{leaf} (Fig. 2). The differences in T_{leaf} as influenced by seaweed extract pulverizations were not statistically significant along with the vegetation period. T_{leaf} was mostly higher than the threshold (between 25 and 30°C) for optimum photosynthesis reaction for grapevines [25], probably due to mild stress emerging from the continental climate condition. T_{leaf} has been proven as one of the most changeable plant physiological responses to environmental variables [21], although it directly affects the plant physiology, adaptation and development. Studies indicated that further increases in the grapevine leaf temperature causes reduction in net photosynthesis [25]. Therefore, proper treatments of the vines to maintain T_{leaf} in optimum ranges would be beneficial for sustainable viticulture.

Fig. 2. Changes in leaf temperature (°C) of ‘Trakya ilkeren’ vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

As expected, chlorophyll content of the grapevine leaf did not show significant variation in the first analysis, although a drastically treatment-dependent variation occurred afterwards (Fig. 3). After the second application, the greatest chlorophyll content was obtained from 0.3% dose (26.1 SPAD unit), which was closely followed by 1.0% dose (25.8 SPAD unit) in the same statistical group. On the other hand, the lowest chlorophyll content was measured in control vines (23.7 SPAD unit) with a significantly lower value than all the doses. Similar cases happened after the third treatment and the changes were apparent during other measurements. In a previous study, in which the effects of leaf seaweed pulverization on the growth of grapevines were aimed to investigate, the seaweed pulverization significantly improved the chlorophyll content of the vines [8].

Fig. 3. Changes in leaf chlorophyll content (SPAD unit) of ‘Trakya ilkeren’ vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

Growth Investigations

Leaf area of the vines showed significant changes according to the seaweed doses (Fig. 4). The highest leaf area was obtained from %0.3 dose (153.1 cm²), followed with %0.5 (148.0 cm²) and %1.0 (147.5 cm²) with the same statistical significance level. The lowest leaf area was found in control (108.4 cm²) which was followed by 2.0% (116.7 cm²). Vegetative development promotion was also recorded by Simsek [26] who treated ‘Klemantin’ trees with seaweed extract. Improvement in leaf area can induce photosynthetic activity since the higher leaf area could lead plant collect much more sunlight [27]. Increase in photosynthesis would

result in much more carbohydrates storage in vine, which in turn support the plant against stressors such as winter freeze or summer drought under continental climate conditions.

Fig. 4. leaf area (cm²) of 'Trakya ilkeren' vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

As illustrated in Fig. 5, shoot length of the vines displayed significant changes in response of doses among which 0.3% seaweed (76.5 cm) was remarkably outstanding. All the seaweed doses significantly improved the shoot length of the vines in comparison to control vines (48.7 cm). Shoot length promotions by the seaweed doses at 0.3%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0% and 0.1% were 36.3%, 22.9%, 21.1%, 19.2% and 12.6%, respectively. Shoot growth improvement is one of the prime purposes for a sustainable grape production under continental climate condition where harsh ecological events adversely affect the vine growth [8,24]. Leaf seaweed pulverization, at 0.3% dose in particular, could support the shoot growth of the vines. The growth promoting effects of seaweed could be attributed to phytochemical substances like plant hormones (auxin, cytokinin, gibberellins), vitamins, enzymes as well as plant nutrients (nitrogen and potassium) N, K₂O) as previously stated by Mughunth et al. [28].

Fig. 5. Changes in shoot length (cm) of 'Trakya ilkeren' vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

Lignified shoot length of the vines was significantly affected by seaweed pulverization doses (Fig. 6). The greatest increase in lignified shoot length was obtained from 0.3% seaweed (47.2 cm) while the lowest value was observed in control vines (24.5 cm). Promotions in lignified shoot length in response to the seaweed doses applied at 0.3%, 1.0%, 0.5%, 2.0% and 0.1% were 48.1%, 32.3%, 30.3%, 24.6% and 14.9%, respectively. Proper lignification in

grapevine shoots (canes) is an important precondition directly influencing the cold hardiness and bud fruitfulness in grapevines [29]. Balanced development between reproductive and vegetative features is essential for longevity of the fruitfulness of vines. In order to support the young vines against winter cold damage, seaweed pulverizations, at 0.3% dose in particular, seem a beneficial practice.

Fig. 6. Changes in lignified shoot length (cm) of 'Trakya ilkeren' vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

Seaweed pulverizations significantly increased the shoot diameter of the vines depending on the applied doses (Fig. 7). The highest shoot diameter value was obtained from %0.3 dose (5.35 mm) which was followed by %1.0 (5.07 mm). All the doses had significantly increased the shoot diameter in comparison to control vines (4.02 mm). Insufficient shoot diameter growth commonly occurs in areas characterized with continental climate, although shoot diameter is among the preconditions for endurance of young vines to cold winter [30]. seaweed treatments, with the greatest effect of 0.3% dose, contributed to enhance the shoot diameter in young vines.

Fig. 7. Changes in shoot diameter (mm) of 'Trakya ilkeren' vines in response to leaf seaweed extract pulverizations at different doses. Error bar stands for the standard deviation of that mean.

CONCLUSION

The present investigations were performed to test the effects of different concentrations (0.0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0%) of foliar seaweed extract treatments on young 'Trakya ilkeren' grapevine physiology and development under the continental climate condition where multiple

stress factors restrict the plant growth and physiology. One-year results of the pot grown grapevines indicated that the seaweed at 0.3% concentration was the most effective treatment to support the leaf stomatal conductance, leaf chlorophyll concentration, leaf area, shoot length and shoot diameter of grapevines, although higher seaweed doses were also beneficial for several parameters. The findings suggest that 0.3% seaweed may be beneficial as an environment friendly application to sustain viticulture under the pressure of ever-increasing climate change events. Further multi-year field studies would yield much more information for wider recommendations.

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